

The Zn(II), Cd(II), Pd(II) and $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ -complexes also display 1 : 1 metal-ligand stoichiometry besides having a water or pyridine molecule. All these compounds were found to be diamagnetic. Based on these data a tetrahedral structure is assigned to Zn(II) and Cd(II) complexes and an octahedral structure to $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ -complex.

The Pd(II) complex indicates three absorption bands with their peaks at 22400, 26300 and 30400 cm^{-1} assignable to the transitions, $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$, $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1E_{1g}$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1A_{2g}$. Thus the Pd(II) complex displays a squareplanar configuration. These results are also in agreement with an earlier finding⁷.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. R. C. Kapoor, Head, Department of Chemistry for providing necessary laboratory facilities and evincing interest in the work.

References

1. R. K. MEHTA and R. K. GUPTA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 50.
2. P. PFEIFFER, W. OFFERMANN and H. WERNER, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1942, 159, 313.
3. S. YAMADA, *Coordina. Chem. Review*, 1966, 1, 415.
4. S. YAMADA, Y. KUGE and K. YAMANOVCHI, *Bull. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 40, 1864.
5. R. H. HOLM, G. W. EVERTTE, JR. and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 7, 83.
6. H. A. JAHN and E. TELLER, *Proc. Royal Soc.*, 1937, 161, 220.
7. R. K. MEHTA and V. C. SINGHI, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1972, 276, 304.

Modified Synthesis of Tris(Biguanide) Cobalt (III) Base and its Salts

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Manuscript received 27 September 1974; accepted 28 January 1975

THE title compounds have been the subject of many investigations : asymmetric transformation of the second order during resolution¹, intramolecular twist mechanism of racemisation², inner sphere formation constant³, aquation kinetics⁴, outer sphere association constants⁵, filter paper and thin layer chromatography⁶. Original synthesis⁷ involved an over-cautious, somewhat cumbersome and lengthy air

oxidation of the insoluble bis(biguanide) cobalt(II) base in presence of alkaline biguanide. We have been successfully using for many years now a quicker H_2O_2 oxidation procedure. A recent report by Krishnamurthy⁸ describing the efficacy of H_2O_2 in radically reducing the time of synthesis of trans- $[\text{CoCl}_2(\text{en})_2] = \text{Cl}(\text{en} = \text{ethylenediamine})$ prompts us to describe our own on $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3](\text{OH})_3$ and its salts.

Biguanide acid sulfate⁹ (8.5 g) was dissolved in water (75 ml) containing NaOH (6.0 g). To this was added with stirring a solution of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2.5 g) in water (5.0 ml) H_2O_2 (5.0 ml, 20 vol.) was added and the mixture heated on a steam bath for 30 min with stirring. The solution along with the red crystals of $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3](\text{OH})_3$ were cooled in ice for 1 hr, filtered and the crystals washed with ice cold ethanol (25 ml.). The base was then triturated with ice cold HCl (1 : 3) to a pH $\sim$ 6.0. The orange red coloured tris(biguanide) cobalt(III) chloride was filtered with the aid of ethanol (10 ml) and was finally recrystallised from hot water (70 ml.). Yield 2.6 g. Found : Cl, 22.74; Co, 12.80; Eq.wt. 156. Calcd.: Cl, 22.88; Co, 12.68; Eq.wt. 156.

The compound gave the two usual transitions ; $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{1g}$ 21.1 kK; $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{2g}$ 28.4 kK.

References

1. P. RAY and N. K. DUTT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 289.
2. P. RAY and N. K. DUTT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 91.
3. A. K. DE, N. N. GHOSH and P. RAY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 33, 846.
4. D. BANERJEA and B. CHAKRAVARTY, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1964, 26, 1233.
5. M. K. DE and R. L. DUTTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 750.
6. R. L. DUTTA, A. BHATTACHARYA and R. K. RAY, (to be published).
7. P. RAY and N. K. DUTT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 621.
8. M. KRISHNAMURTHY, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1972, 34, 3915.
9. D. KARIPIDES and W. C. FERNELIUS, 'Inorganic Syntheses', Vol. VII, Ed. J. Kleinberg, McGraw-Hill Book Co., Inc., New York, 1963, p. 56.

Estimation of Ba^{2+} , Ag^+ and Tl^+ as chromates by A.C. Amperometry

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Manuscript received 3 December 1974; accepted 25 February 1975

KOLTHOFF and Gregor^{1,2} estimated barium with chromate ion in aqueous and aqueous-ethanol mixtures by conventional amperometric titration which yielded results that were 2 to 5% low. Many

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